

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: MDIA

COURSE CODE: ACA - 401

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word (2020)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. The danger of plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-6)
3. Citations and quotations (EUCLID 2021, 6-7)
4. Grammar rules (EUCLID 2021, 6-7)
5. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-28)
6. Diverse English Jargons (EUCLID 2021, 31-34)
7. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2021, 31-34)

ACADEMIC WRITING

1) **INTRODUCTION**

ACA-401 is the very first course of EUCLID's Master of Science Diplomacy and International Affairs. This course aims at bringing newly enrolled students the fundamental know-how in writing their different assignments. Now I will show how far period one, through its study materials, gave me an insight into how a good academic writing should look like.

2) **THE ESSENTIAL POINTS FROM PERIOD ONE**

Many grammar points discussed in this document are part of my English lessons from secondary school. They refresh my mind on basic English rules and deepen my knowledge in many aspects.

Thus, as the reading document points out, essay writing demands a certain amount of creativity and critical spirit aligned with adequate preparation, yielding an essay worth the read –persuasive and enjoyable to its reader. Therefore, it is right to assume that success

depends on the time spent from the drafting to the achievement of the whole work. And an essay must always present its three components: Introduction, Body (Development), and conclusion.

Furthermore, the authors clearly emphasize plagiarism. I find this very useful due to the significant number of written assignments we have to deal with throughout the program. Among tools to avoid plagiarism, we need to constantly "properly cite the author or source that has provided the information we are using" (EUCLID 2021, 6). An academic "crime" with severe consequences, plagiarism can even lead to the loss of a position or a job many years later. It is the case of the German Federal Minister of Family, Elderly, Women, And Youth, who was recently "forced" to leave the government after some plagiarism accusations. So far, plagiarism can lead us. There are two ways for quoting depending on what we quote or cite and how long it is. The only alternative to quoting is paraphrasing, telling in our own words someone's sayings or words.

Another point is the use of American and British English in academic writing. EUCLID gives me the possibility of choice between the two. I feel more comfortable with American English and will write all assignments using it. "American English has grown significantly in international significance since World War Two" (EUCLID 2021, 27)

EUCLID provides a premium *Grammarly* subscription to help students minimize grammar mistakes in their written assignments. This is a labor-saving and valuable resource for Euclid students.

In addition to all recommendations provided in this "masterpiece," I would like to emphasize that reading a lot to have a broader general knowledge is of great interest to succeed within the MDIA Program. As well as having a profound insight into current political and social happenings will be advantageous.

As I will sometimes need to refer online materials, I find it important to make clear that no Wikipedia information should be cited. *Wikipedia* is one of the most significant online encyclopedias but does not always provide reliable and up to date information.

As for the Chicago Manual of Style. It has been clearly exposed and well-detailed in the support document. Its numerous indications are not confusing but rather instructive and easy to learn.

3) CONCLUSION

I would finally assume that period one of ACA-401 is a good "entry" into the MDIA course. This PDF study material provided by Dr. Gulma and Pr. Cleenewerck is an essential asset that will accompany me all along the course. The most important thing in this program is, however, the rules on how to avoid plagiarism. Re-reading all the golden recommendations found in this document will surely help us achieve the goal of an academic writing expected from a mater's student at Euclid University.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 3rd ed. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.